

Exploring the building blocks of sustainable social housing frameworks

Mahmoud Alsaeed, Karim Hadjri, Krzysztof Nawratek

School of Architecture, The University of Sheffield, Sheffield, the UK

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1. Introduction

The nexus between housing and sustainability is a multi-layered discourse often characterised by its ambiguity and complexity (Matthews, 2016). The realisation of large-scale, sustainable social housing projects is therefore associated with various challenges which require a comprehensive and systematic approach that transcends disciplinary boundaries. At the centre of this approach are frameworks that serve as fundamental constructs for planning and decision-making processes (Moghayedi et al., 2021). These frameworks embody a structured system of rules and ideologies that act as a supportive scaffold on which decisions are formulated. They also facilitate the formulation of standardised practices, principles, and detailed operational guidelines for sustainable housing provisions.

The development of a robust framework, regardless of its nature, requires the definition of a core set of pillars with careful attention to their structuring, organisation and interlinkage. Furthermore, these pillars are crucial in addressing real-world challenges that arise from both theoretical and practical perspectives in the delivery of sustainable social housing. To this end, the parameters that define social housing and sustainable housing frameworks are first examined through an exploratory literature review. Then, the challenges associated with the delivery of sustainable housing are identified through a synthesis of literature and semi-structured interviews with housing associations, designers, and sustainability specialists.

A trilogy of pillars needed for the development of sustainable social housing frameworks is proposed; this is established around three thematic areas: Sustainability and its dimensions, social housing processes and perceptions, and the roles and responsibilities of public authorities. It is important to note that while this mapping represents a first step for housing researchers and industry professionals seeking to develop operational frameworks for sustainable social housing projects, it is not itself a framework. Instead, it lays the foundation for a common understanding of future sustainable social housing frameworks.

2. Context

The theoretical context of this paper is based on three pillars, starting with the definition criteria of social housing, then the concepts of sustainable social housing and the sustainability frameworks that are often used in housing provisions.

2.1 Social housing narratives

As social housing is highly context-dependent, there is no universal definition. Nonetheless, critical concepts from scholars such as Harriott et al. (2004); Malpass & Victory (2010); Priemus (2013); Oyebanji (2014); Stephens (2013); and others are presented. In its broadest sense, social housing encompasses a housing model with four defining features. Firstly, the type of

beneficiaries (target groups) often denotes housing availability to specific population groups. Secondly, the funding mechanisms (subsidies) usually involve significant public support. Thirdly, the type of provider varies, ranging from public bodies in the case of councils housing to third-sector organisations such as housing associations. Fourthly, ownership options include social renting or shared ownership. Consequently, social housing functions as a "system" that provides housing to households with limited means, ensuring their needs are met through public subsidies (Granath Hansson & Lundgren, 2019). Local authorities, housing associations and other non-profit and for-profit organisations are involved in the provision and management of social housing, all of which are subject to government regulation (Harriott et al., 2004).

Given the highly context-dependent nature of social housing, it is not possible to define it in a universal sense. Nevertheless, the work of scholars such as Harriott et al. (2004), Malpass & Victory (2010), Priemus (2013), Oyebanji (2014), Stephens (2013), and others is referenced in order to present critical concepts. In its broadest sense, social housing can be defined as a housing model that is characterised by four defining features. Firstly, the type of beneficiary (target group) frequently indicates the availability of housing for particular population groups. Secondly, the funding mechanisms, which typically take the form of subsidies, often entail substantial public support. Thirdly, the type of provider varies, encompassing both public bodies, as exemplified by councils housing, and third-sector organisations, such as housing associations. Fourthly, there are two principal forms of ownership: social renting and shared ownership. Consequently, social housing functions as a "system" that provides housing to households with limited means, provided that their needs, often supported by public subsidies, are confirmed (Granath Hansson & Lundgren, 2019). Local authorities, housing associations, and other non-profit and for-profit organisations are involved in the provision and management of social housing, all of which are subject to government regulation (Harriott et al., 2004).

2.2 Sustainable social housing structure

The term "sustainable social housing" lacks a generally accepted definition. Instead, it encompasses a continuum of terms and concepts from different sources which have been explored and mapped in this article. The rationale behind this approach is the need to clarify the existing narratives and highlight the similarities and differences between these concepts and any links contributing to the overarching perception of sustainable social housing. To this end, the work of Kruger & Seville (2012), Murphy (2003), Udomiaye et al. (2018), Attia (2016), and Peters (2013) was reviewed. However, the reviewed literature does not provide a precise classification method for the concepts in question. A classification is, therefore, proposed (Figure 1) based on (1) definitional groups, defined by the authors with similar views on the meaning of sustainable buildings, (2) the terminology used to describe the building system, which typically represents a relationship between the building and the environment, and (3) the definition criteria that explain the terminologies used and the inter-relations between humans, the built environment, and nature.

Figure 1. Sustainable housing concepts. Source: Authors, 2024

Three different groups of definitions emerged from this mapping. Firstly, the definition by the buildings impact: the scholars in this category highlight the need to minimise the negative impact of the built environment on natural ecosystems. Secondly, the building performance definition demonstrates the superiority of building systems in terms of electricity consumption, water consumption and heating and cooling efficiency. Thirdly, by design principle, scholars in this group use proven design methods to explain how buildings can be made more sustainable. They suggest moving away from conventional heating and cooling systems to make ecosystems healthier and more resilient.

Although this classification and mapping are rather argumentative, they feed directly into the development of the concept of the sustainable building components, which are advocated as one of the critical dimensions of sustainable social housing.

2.3 Sustainable social housing structure

In response to the complexity of sustainability, several frameworks have been created to guide the development process and clarify possible areas for intervention. These frameworks are also known as sustainability assessment and certification schemes. To identify and map the components of the most prominent sustainability frameworks, the recent Policy Playbook published by the UK Green Buildings Council (2020), the Handbook of best practices published by Housing Europe (2023), as well as the work of Knox (2015); Fokaidis et al (2017); Garde (2009); Kubba (2012) and others, were examined. Six primary frameworks emerged as the predominant systems currently used by practitioners (Figure 2). These frameworks were analysed through descriptive definitions of their structure and the areas of intervention they support. In addition, the relationships between these areas were clarified by examining the scope of their intervention. For example, when assessing the sustainable location criterion, both the Leadership in Energy

and Environmental Design (LEED) and the Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM) show a common interest in promoting and facilitating the use of well-connected sites, emphasising the use of existing infrastructure. In contrast, ISO 14001 focuses on establishing guidelines and standardised processes for environmental management, rather than targeting specific criteria.

Figure 2. Identified sustainability frameworks. Source: Authors as adapted from BRE (2016); Kubba (2012) and others

To map the components of these systems, the explanation of the field of intervention, which is often aimed at building systems, human welfare, or policy development, was examined. Therefore, a trilogy of classifications is formed that explains the rationale behind these system constructs. While LEED and BREEAM are building-centric and focus on building system improvement to support ecological systems, the second class, such as the WELL Building Standards, was created to put well-being and health at the heart of building design and construction. The third class is policy-centric and focuses on the role of policy in balancing building systems, natural systems, and human well-being. To this end, environmental sustainability, regardless of the assessment approach or system, must strike a perfect balance between human needs, health and well-being, and the built environment (Poveda & Lipsett, 2011).

3. Methods

This study used a dual method consisting of an exploratory literature review and semi-structured interviews. The literature was examined using sources such as peer-reviewed articles, books, and other documents from specialised databases, including the Web of Science. A combination of keywords was used, such as sustainability framework, social housing, and sustainability in housing. The search's temporal scope was limited to the 2000s onward. A selection criterion based on the parameters of relevance, authority, and influence, as described by Mensah and Enu-Kwesi (2018), was used to narrow down a pool of 400 sources to 50 sources that were deemed most relevant to this study. The selected literature was then analysed to compare and contrast

the narratives on the topics under investigation. The analysis results were then mapped to build the argumentation of the findings.

The semi-structured interviews, on the other hand, helped to gain insights into the challenges of developing sustainable social housing from the practice perspective by either confirming existing theoretical narratives or uncovering new insights. Between September 2022 and November 2023, 25 interviews were conducted with various stakeholders from England, including development and asset managers, sustainability team leaders from housing associations, design architects and planners from architectural practices, and sustainability designers and systems specialists from sustainability services providers.

The questions followed a funnelled structure and began with general enquiries about the participants' definitions of sustainability and social housing. They then moved on to integrating sustainability into housing and finally to identifying challenges and the strategies to overcome them. The data collected was analysed thematically using NVivo software. An inductive coding approach was followed, as Joffe & Yardley (2003) explained, considering the principles of reliability and validity. The resulting themes were grouped around three overarching codes: funding, practices and associated challenges, and the role of regulators in sustainable housing development. The outcome of the analysis was then structured to describe the challenges related to sustainable practices in social housing, and to clarify weaknesses and areas for further investigation in the development of sustainable social housing frameworks.

4. Findings

This section describes the findings of this study. It is structured to present the construct of sustainable social housing and the components of the existing sustainability framework and ends with the challenges in practice. To answer the question of what constitutes the construct of sustainable social housing, it is imperative to align the insights gained from the literature reviewed and the interviews. Therefore, Figure 3 was created to outline the identified components of the narratives. This outline begins with the conventional definition of social housing, as a housing system tailored to specific demographic groups that promote social integration and are overseen and supported by specialised and public agencies. Consequently, “sustainable social housing” is proposed as a system and a development model that encompasses a quadrant of concepts.

Firstly, it promotes the adaptation and integration of sustainable building features and characteristics with the aim of mitigating negative environmental impacts, promoting resource efficiency and reducing carbon emissions. This particular focus revolves around the building components, including the physical characteristics of the structure such as building systems, energy efficiency measures and water conservation strategies. It also considers the human experience, explaining and examining the elements of the building that interact with occupants, such as the quality of the indoor and outdoor environment and structural considerations to improve occupant wellbeing. Secondly, it addresses social cohesion and the well-being of residents by promoting social benefits and creating a healthy and comfortable living environment. Thirdly, it focuses on the economic sustainability of the building, which aims to reduce energy consumption and operating costs while minimising maintenance expenditure. Fourthly, it recognises the central role of the public sector in disbursing subsidies, promoting transparent governance models, and regulating practices through established rules and guidelines.

Figure 3. Sustainable social housing narratives construct. Source: Authors, 2024

Three different categories of challenges emerge from the interviews. The organisational challenges relate primarily to the role of authorities and government agencies in sustainability in the housing sector. This encompasses diverse issues such as policy complexity, fragmentation, and potential misinterpretation of regulations objectives. A notable challenge is the scarcity of funds and investments allocated to sustainable social housing initiatives. Secondly, methodological challenges underscore the pivotal role of practical implementation in sustainable housing provision. Participants highlighted concerns regarding the absence of data, sustainable supply chain management, inadequate funding streams, and insufficient collaboration among developers, hindering effective implementation strategies. Lastly, fiscal challenges centre on the financial feasibility of development projects when integrating sustainability principles. This includes challenges regarding a clear housing vision, contributing to market instability and impeding long-term planning efforts.

5. Conclusion

Based on the sustainable social housing narratives described in Figure 3, and the insights gained from interviews, it was concluded that when a framework for sustainable social housing is proposed, it should be structured around three defining pillars: Housing, Sustainability and Regulatory structure.

- The first pillar refers to the essential criteria that define social housing (such as tenure, provider participation, target group and financing mechanisms). It sets out a clear explanation of the operational parameters of the social housing frameworks and responds to the methodological challenges of the sector.
- The second pillar determines sustainability as a crucial theme encompassing various dimensions, including mitigating environmental impact, integrating energy-efficient and resilient building components, promoting resident well-being through thoughtful design and amenity, and assessing economic viability over the lifecycle of the housing project. This pillar ensures that housing initiatives not only meet immediate needs but also positively contribute to the well-being of the environment and the community in the long term.
- The third pillar focuses on optimising the regulatory framework for social housing and sustainability integration. By simplifying processes and regulations, obstacles can be minimised, project realisation can be accelerated, and innovation and efficiency within the sector can be promoted. This pillar must also set aims to promote a favourable environment for the sustainable development of social housing among practitioners and providers.

In addition, it is essential to recognise and address cross-cutting challenges that intersect these pillars. These challenges include organisational aspects, methodological approaches and fiscal considerations. Proactively identifying and mitigating these challenges will improve the framework's ability to manage complexity and ensure that it effectively achieves the goals of sustainable social housing. By integrating these pillars and addressing overarching challenges, a robust framework can be developed to meet immediate housing needs while advancing broader social, environmental and economic goals for the future.

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